

Stability Constants of Mercury(II), Copper(II), Lead(II) and Uranium(II)dioxide Complexes with Pyruvate

MAHMOUD GHANDOUR*

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science (Assiut), Assiut University, Egypt

and

HESHAM I IANSOUR and MAHMOUD KHODARY

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, (Qena), Assiut University, Egypt

Manuscript received 16 April 1984, accepted 15 August 1984

Potentiometric titration technique is applied to study the complexes of Cu^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} with pyruvate at different ionic strengths and temperatures. 1:1 metal to ligand complexes are formed with the bivalent copper, mercury and lead ions whereas uranyl ion forms 1:1 and 1:2 metal to ligand complexes. The thermodynamic functions, ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° are determined.

THE metal complexes with pyruvate (2-oxopropionate) are important because of the essential biological role of pyruvic acid. Reports concerning the stoichiometry of the bivalent metal pyruvate complexes are diverse. Complexes of the type ML^+ (L=pyruvate) have been reported with bivalent Cu^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Ca , Fe and Cd^{2+} . On the other hand, complexes of the type ML^+ and ML_2 are detected with Cu^{2+} , Ni and Zn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} ions. It is of interest to investigate the complexes of bivalent Cu , Pb , Hg and UO_2 ions with pyruvate in order to throw more light on the stoichiometry of the complexes and to determine the stability constants and thermodynamic functions.

Experimental

Calvin-Bjerrum's technique as adapted by Irving and Rossotti⁹ was used to determine the proton-ligand association constant and formation constants of the pyruvate complexes with Cu^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} .

pH measurements were carried out on Orion Research model 601 digital ionalyzer pH meter. Oxygen was removed by bubbling pure nitrogen during titrations. The solutions of HgCl_2 (Cambrian), CuCl_2 (Prolabo) and $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (B.D.H.) were prepared from the chemically pure grade and titrated complexometrically by EDTA. UO_2Cl_2 (B.D.H.) was prepared and checked as U_3O_8 . Solutions of perchloric acid (B.D.H., A.R.) and pyruvic acid (Prolabo) were prepared and standardised alkalimetrically. Sodium perchlorate solution (2 M) was used to adjust the ionic strength.

Potentiometric titrations of pyruvic acid (0.03 M) in presence of the metal salt solution, the ratio of acid to metal being 6:1, were carried out at 25° and at different ionic strengths, viz. 0.03-0.11 M,

using carbonate-free sodium hydroxide solution (0.55 M). The titrations were also performed at temperatures ranging from 30 to 50° ($\mu=0.1$) in order to calculate reaction enthalpy and entropy values.

Fig. 1. Titration curves of 50 ml, (a) 0.03 M HClO_4 , (b) a + 0.03 M pyruvic acid, (c) b + 5×10^{-3} M Cu^{2+} , (d) b + 5×10^{-3} M UO_2^{2+} with 0.55 M NaOH.

Results and Discussion

The representative curves shown in Fig. 1 indicate that the metal-ligand titration curve is well separated from the ligand titration curve. Thus, replacement of hydrogen ion is due to complexation. It has been noticed that solid phase appeared at $pH \approx 5$ in the metal-ligand titration curves.

The values of \bar{n}_A (average number of H^+ ions attached per ligand) were plotted against pH . Interpolation at half \bar{n}_A values give the protonation constant of the ligand, $\log K^H$. The $\log K^H$ obtained at different ionic strengths at 25° and at different temperatures ($\mu=0.1$) are listed in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS ($\log k$) OF PYRUVATE COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS AT 25°

μ M	H^+	Cu^{2+}	Hg^{2+}	Pb^{2+}	UO_2^{2+}		
					K_1	K_2	β
0.0*	2.75	2.14	2.32	2.67	2.39	2.11	4.5
0.03	2.48	1.87	2.10	2.36	2.07	1.86	3.93
0.05	2.38	1.78	1.95	2.16	2.02	1.86	3.88
0.07	2.34	1.70	1.84	2.04	1.93	1.83	3.76
0.09	2.29	1.67	1.69	1.84	1.88	1.80	3.68
0.11	2.20	1.64	1.63	1.72	1.79	1.78	3.57

* Obtained from the linear plots $\log k$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS ($\log k$) OF PYRUVATE COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT TEMP

Temp. $^\circ C$	$\mu = 0.1 M NaClO_4$				UO_2^{2+}		
	H^+	Cu^{2+}	Hg^{2+}	Pb^{2+}	K_1	K_2	β_2^*
30	2.10	1.67	1.69	1.85	1.88	1.81	3.69
35	2.00	1.75	—	—	1.92	1.85	3.77
40	1.95	1.81	1.76	2.07	1.96	1.86	3.82
45	1.85	1.85	—	—	2.05	1.87	3.92
50	1.78	1.89	2.00	2.12	2.11	1.92	4.03

The metal-ligand stability constants were obtained from the curves drawn between \bar{n} (average number of ligands attached per metal ion) and pL (free ligand exponent). The formation of only 1:1 complexes of Cu^{2+} , Hg^{2+} and Pb^{2+} were obtained from interpolation at $\bar{n}=0.5$. On the other hand, interpolation at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and 1.5 gave the formation constants of 1:1, and 1:2 for uranyl pyruvate complexes.

Effect of ionic strength: The stability constants of the metal pyruvate complexes and the protonation constant of pyruvate at different ionic strengths at 25° reveal that $\log K$ and $\log K^H$ gradually decrease with increasing ionic strength. The thermodynamic stability constants were obtained by extrapolating the linear plots of $\log K$ and $\log K^H$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ to zero ionic strength (Table 1). Representative \bar{n} vs pL plots are shown in Fig. 2.

Effect of temperature: The $\log K$ values, for both pyruvic acid and its metal complexes vs $1/T$ were linear. ΔG^* , ΔH^* and ΔS^* parameters are reported in Table 3. Moreover, the value of the

standard free energy was obtained from $\Delta G^* = -2.303 RT \log K^{\mu=0}$, where $K^{\mu=0}$ is the extrapolated

Fig. 2. Formation curves of UO_2 -pyruvate complexes at μ (a) 0.03, (b) 0.05, (c) 0.07, (d) 0.09 and (e) 0.11 M.

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF PROTONATION AND COMPLEX FORMATION

Parameter	$\mu = 0.1 M$, Temp. 30°				
	H^+	Cu^{2+}	Hg^{2+}	Pb^{2+}	UO_2^{2+}
$-\Delta G^*$ kcal mol $^{-1}$	2.91	2.32	2.34	2.57	5.11
ΔH^* kcal mol $^{-1}$	-6.86	4.75	7.63	6.10	7.31
ΔS^* kcal mol $^{-1}$	-13.04	23.33	32.90	28.61	40.99
$-\Delta G^*$ kcal mol $^{-1}$ ($\mu \rightarrow 0$)	3.75	2.92	3.75	4.36	6.14

value of the formation constant at zero ionic strength. The order of increase in ΔS^* values is the same as that of formation constants. The formation constants are seen to be larger at 50° than at 30° (Fig. 3). Endothermic heats are not uncommon in reactions where electrostatic interactions predominate². On the other hand, HL formation constant seems to be exothermic.

Fig. 3. Formation curves of Cu -pyruvate complex at (a) 50° , (b) 45° , (c) 40° , (d) 35° and (e) 30° .

According to the data obtained by Dazzi and Falqui³, the protonation of the ligand is endothermic and the formation of lead pyruvate complex is exothermic. The only difference in the experimental condition is the use of 1.0 M KNO₃. However, our results are in accordance with those obtained by Leussing and Shultz² concerning the effect of temperature on the protonation of pyruvate anion and some metal pyruvate complexes.

Comparing the values of pK_a for pyruvic acid at 25°, reported earlier, viz. 2.40 (3 M NaClO₄)⁴, 2.20 (0.3 M NaClO₄)⁴, 2.49 ($\mu \rightarrow 0$)¹⁰, 2.35 (0.5 M KCl)¹¹, 2.39 (0.65 M KCl)³, 2.10 (M NaCl)¹² and 2.34 (M KNO₃)⁵, with those obtained in the present investigation indicates their reliability.

Thus, in water pyruvic acid forms 1 : 1 metal to ligand complexes with Cu^{II}, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} ions. The results are in accordance with those reported earlier^{1,3} for Cu^{II} and Pb^{II} pyruvate complexes. The formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 uranyl pyruvate complexes is confirmed^{1,8}.

However, the formation of other complexes with 1 : 2 metal to ligand ratios were reported^{5,7} for Cu^{II} and Pb^{II}. No datum is available for Hg^{II} pyruvate complexes for comparison. It has been shown that other bivalent metal cations, such as Mn, Ca, Fe and Cd form but weaker 1 : 1 metal pyruvate complexes^{3,4}.

It was proved³ by chemical and spectrometrical data that the structure of the PbL⁺ complex forms a

five-membered ring consisting of carboxylic group, the metal ion and the oxo group, viz.

It is assumed that the same structure can be formulated for the other 1 : 1 bivalent metal complexes with pyruvate.

References

1. S. RAMAMOORTHY, A. RAGHAVAN, V. R. VIJAYAROGHAVAN and M. SANTAPPA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, 31, 1851.
2. D. L. LEUSSING and D. C. SCHULTZ, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 4846.
3. E. DAZZI and M. T. FALQUI, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1976, 106, 1095.
4. O. FORSBERG, B. GELLAND, P. ULMGREN and O. WAHLBERG, *Acta Chem. Scand., Ser. A*, 1978, 32, 345.
5. E. GELLES and R. W. HAY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3673.
6. D. E. TALLMAN and D. L. LEUSSING, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 91, 6253.
7. B. LENARCIK and Z. WARNEKE, *Rocz. Chem.*, 1969, 43, 1329.
8. S. RAMAMOORTHY and M. SANTAPPA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1968, 37, 403.
9. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
10. K. J. PEDERSON, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1952, 6, 243.
11. D. L. LEUSSING and E. M. HANNA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 88, 693.
12. D. E. TALLMAN and D. L. LEUSSING, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 91, 6253.